

A Modelling Investigation of Thermal Effects on Matrix Cracking and Delamination in Composite T-piece Specimens

J Chen

Faculty of Technology, University of Portsmouth
Portsmouth, PO1 3AH, UK
jiye.chen@port.ac.uk

SUMMARY

This paper investigates the curing temperature effects on matrix crack initiation and delamination in composite T-piece specimens using a modified interface cohesive model with thermal effects. Thermal shrinkage cracking in the deltoid region of T-piece was simulated. Thermal effect on the prediction of dominated delamination was also studied.

Keywords: Thermal shrinkage crack, Delamination, T-piece specimen, Interface cohesive model, FEA

INTRODUCTION

Study of composite T-piece specimens has received sound attention as it is an important component in aerospace structures and wind turbine blades. Thermal effects from manufacture will remain in components as residual stresses or strains, and also possibly incur thermal shrinkage cracking in matrix. This was evidence in manufacturing some T-piece specimens, and in some particular manufacture of wind turbine blades. Investigation of thermal effects on matrix cracking and delamination mechanism will benefit the design and manufacture of such composite components. Figure 1 shows the local failure pattern in the area of deltoid of T-piece, which presents initial thermal shrinkage crack, initial delamination point and dominated delamination. Previous investigations [1] studied basic failure mechanism of T-piece under T-pull loading. This paper aims to investigate the thermal effect on matrix crack initiation in the deltoid region and a dominated delamination along the interface between radius laminates and deltoid of T-piece. A temperature change 175°C^0 from curing laminates and mechanical T-pull loading are considered in this investigation. Basic materials of laminates, geometry of T-piece and T-pull loading and clamped restraints on the foot of T-piece are taken from reference 1. The temperature change 175°C^0 is used to investigate the thermal shrinkage cracking in the deltoid and also used to study the thermal effects on the prediction of a dominated delamination.

A MODIFIED COHESIVE INTERFACE MODEL WITH THERMAL EFFECTS

The numerical approach in this work uses a modified interface cohesive model which considers thermal and mechanical relative displacements together for the study of cohesive interfacial behaviour. The damage initiation can be assessed by a quadratic formula given in equ. 1.

$$\left(\frac{\varepsilon_I}{\varepsilon_{I0}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\varepsilon_{II}}{\varepsilon_{II0}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\varepsilon_{III}}{\varepsilon_{III0}}\right)^2 = 1 \quad (1)$$

Where, ε_{I0} , ε_{II0} and ε_{III0} are the interfacial initial damage relative displacement with thermal effects corresponding to mode I, mode II and mode III fracture respectively. Equ. 1 is a combined initial damage mode considered the coupling effects, which determines the point where materials begin softening. Each relative displacement ε_j (j=I, II, III) in equ.1 can be accounted by a simple superposition as

$$\varepsilon_j = \varepsilon_{jt} + \varepsilon_{jm} \quad (2)$$

or by a quadratic relationship

$$\varepsilon_j = \sqrt{\varepsilon_{jt}^2 + \varepsilon_{jm}^2} \quad (3)$$

for each fracture mode. In equations 2 and 3, ε_{jm} is usual mechanical relative displacement [1-4], ε_{jt} is the thermal relative displacement component, which can be accounted by the following equation.

$$\varepsilon_{jt} = \alpha_j \Delta T \quad (4)$$

Where, thermal coefficient α_j varies with composite material directions, which can be seen in the Table 1. ΔT is the temperature change referred to the manufacturing conditions for composite components.

Delamination propagation can be assessed by the mixed mode energy criteria power law [1-12] shown in equ. 5 in this investigation.

$$\left(\frac{G_I}{G_{Ic}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_{IIc}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{G_{III}}{G_{IIIc}}\right)^2 = 1 \quad (5)$$

Where, G_{Ic} , G_{IIc} and G_{IIIc} are the fracture toughness corresponding to mode I, mode II and mode III crack respectively. Each fracture toughness G_{jc} in equ. 5 determines the area under bilinear lines shown in Figure 5 which is a material softening damage law. Each strain energy release rate G_j in equ. 5 can be accounted by equ. 6 when fracture occurs.

$$G_{jc} = \int_0^{\sigma_{jt}} \varepsilon_j d\sigma_j \quad (6)$$

Substituting (2) into (6) results the following equation.

$$G_{jc} = \int_0^{\sigma_{jt}} (\varepsilon_{jt}(\Delta T) + \varepsilon_{jm}(\sigma_j)) d\sigma_j \quad (7)$$

Using equ. 7 the constitution of interface cohesive element can be expressed as a same format as that in references 2 to 4 as follows.

$$\mathbf{K}_t = \int_A \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{D}_t \mathbf{B} dA \quad (8)$$

In equ. 8, \mathbf{B} is the matrix of nodal shape functions of interface cohesive element that relates the nodal relative displacements, \mathbf{A} , of interface area, which can be seen in detailed in [2-4], and \mathbf{D}_t is the cohesive material constitutive relationship, which is given by the derivation of tractions as follows.

$$[\mathbf{D}_t] = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \sigma_I}{\partial \varepsilon_I} & \frac{\partial \sigma_I}{\partial \varepsilon_{II}} \\ \frac{\partial \sigma_{II}}{\partial \varepsilon_I} & \frac{\partial \sigma_{II}}{\partial \varepsilon_{II}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

In equ. 9, the normal and tangential components of the traction acting on the interface in the cohesive process zone can be derived by the relationship between tractions and relative displacements, expressed by the equ. 10 [2-4].

$$\sigma_j(\varepsilon) = \begin{cases} K_0 \varepsilon_0 & \text{if } \varepsilon_j < \varepsilon_0 \\ (1-d)K_0 \varepsilon_0 & \text{if } \varepsilon_0 < \varepsilon_j < \varepsilon_{jc}, \quad j = I, II, III \\ 0 & \text{if } \varepsilon_j > \varepsilon_{jc} \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

Where, analytically, the damage scale d can be expressed by a quadratic relationship

$$d = \sqrt{d_I^2 + d_{II}^2 + d_{III}^2} \quad (11)$$

Where,

$$d_j = \frac{(\varepsilon_{jt} + \varepsilon_{jm} - \varepsilon_0)\varepsilon_{jc}}{(\varepsilon_{jc} - \varepsilon_0)(\varepsilon_{jt} + \varepsilon_{jm})}, \quad j = I, II, III \quad (12)$$

Equations 1 to 12 were used to develop a linear 2D interface cohesive element shown in Figure 6 through a user subroutine in ABAQUS [13]. This is a modified interface cohesive model used in the investigation of thermal effects on matrix cracking and delamination in this paper.

MODELLING THERMAL SHRINKAGE CRACKING

A half plane strain model of T-piece is shown in Figure 3. Four-noded quadrilateral plane strain elements CPE4I from ABAQUS were employed in this modelling, interface cohesive user elements were inserted in the potential crack area i.e. deltoid region, and the interface between laminate radius and deltoid. Mesh density in crack potential area is controlled by the critical length given in the reference 1. A released restraint condition was applied firstly to study the effect of temperature change from curing laminates on the behavior of T-piece. The temperature change 175°C^0 as a thermal loading was applied in the entire mesh of T-piece. General material properties and fracture toughness are given in the Table 1 and 2 respectively. Figure 2a shows the deformed deltoid region in a half mesh which shows that there is no significant cracking presented by interface cohesive models. When the restraint was given by clamping the foot of T-piece, compression in the deltoid was observed and material compressive failure presented by interface cohesive elements is shown in Figure 2b. This implicates that materials would fail in deltoid when improper restraints are applied in curing laminates, and failed materials will form cracks in the deltoid when specimens cool down and restraints are released after curing.

THERMAL EFFECTS ON DELAMINATION

Figure 3 also shows thermal shrinkage cracking and delamination in deltoid region. Failure response of two loading cases, pull and pull plus thermal effect, are given in Figure 4 which shows that thermal effect on delamination is not significant, reduced failure load due to thermal initial cracking can be ignored in this case. Predicted failure load is 54.9N and 54.1N for T-pull loading case and T-pull plus thermal effects respectively. Both predicted failure loads are close to the tested average failure load 55N reported in reference 1. This proves that radius laminates is the main load carrier in the T-pull loading case although there is an initial crack in the deltoid of T-piece.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

A modified interface cohesive model with thermal effects was presented in this paper. This model was successfully used to simulate the thermal effects on matrix cracking and delamination of T-piece specimens. Investigation indicated that any improper restraints

to T-piece specimens in curing process will bring so called thermal shrinkage cracks in deltoid region. However, this sort of initial crack does not affect significantly the capacity of T-piece to resist T-pull loading, the major loading case for similar components such as aero engines blades. Future work includes investigation of thermal effects on matrix cracking and delamination of T-piece specimens under bending and T-pull plus bending case.

REFERENCES

1. J. Chen , E. Ravey, S. Hallett, M. Wisnom and M. Grassi, PREDICTION OF DELAMINATION IN BRAIDED COMPOSITE T-PIECE SPECIMEN, *Composite Science and Technology* (in press), 2009.
2. Chen J, Crisfield MA and Kinloch AJ, Predicting progressive delamination of composite material specimens via interface elements. *Mechanics of Composite Materials and Structures*, 1999, 6:301-317.
3. J. Chen, “Predicting progressive delamination of stiffened fibre-composite panel and repaired sandwich panel by decohesion model”, *Journal of Thermoplastic Composite Materials*, Vol.15, No.5, p429-442, 2002.
4. J. Chen and A. New, “Application of decohesive model with mixed damage scale in fracture analysis of composite materials”, *International Journal of Fatigue & Fracture of Engineering Materials & Structures*, 24(11), p761-769, 2001.
5. P. Rahulkumar, A. Jagota, S. J. Bennison and S. Saigal, Polymer interfacial fracture simulations using cohesive elements, *Acta mater*, 47, Nos 15, p4161-4169, 1999.
6. Vinay K. GOYAL, Eric R. Johnson, Carlos G. Davila, Irreversible constitutive law for modeling the delamination process using interface surface discontinuities, *Composite Structures*, 65, p289-305, 2004.
7. G. A. O. Davis, D. Hitchings, J. Ankersen, Predicting delamination and debonding in modern aerospace composite structures, *Composite Science and Technology*, 66, p846-854, 2006.
8. Robinson P, Galvanetto U, Tumino D, Bellucci G, Violeau D. Numerical simulation of fatigue-driven delamination using interface elements. *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering* 2005; 63:1824-1848.
9. K. L. Roe, T. Siegmund, An irreversible cohesive zone model for interface fatigue crack growth simulation, *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, 70, p209-232, 2003.
10. Peerlings, R. H. J., Brekelmans, W. A. M., de Borst, R., Geers, M. G. D., Gradient-enhanced damage modelling of high-cycle fatigue, *Int. J. Numer. Meth. Engng.* 49, p1547-1569, 2001.
11. A. Turon, J. Costa, P. P. Camanho, C. G. Davila, Simulation of delamination in composites under high-cycle fatigue loading, *Composites Part A*, 38 (11), p.2270-2282, Nov 2007.
12. Rosen T. Tenchev and Brain G. Falzon, Static and Fatigue analysis of delamination in composites, 10th Jubilee National Congress on Theoretical and Applied Mechanics Varna 13-16 September 2005.
13. ABAQUS User Manual, Hibbit, Karlsson & Sorensen Inc., 1080 Main Street, RI02860 4847, USA.

Fig. 1: Failure modes of T-piece specimen

Fig 2: Deformed deltoid region in a half mesh due to thermal effects, a): without restraints, b): with restraints

Fig. 3: Delamination under pull and thermal effects to T-piece's delamination

Fig. 4: Failure response

Figure 5 A bilinear softening damage law

Figure 6 A linear 2D interface cohesive element

Table 1

	E11 (GPa)	E22 (GPa)	E33 (GPa)	G12 (GPa)	G13 (GPa)	G23 (GPa)	ν_{12}	ν_{13}	ν_{23}	α_{11}	α_{22}	α_{33}
Outer Braided Wrap	59.7	60.1	9.7	21.95	4.7	4.7	0.279	0.28	0.28	1.94e-6	2.22e-6	2.8e-5
Braided UD layer	160	9.7	9.7	5.9	5.9	4.7	0.33	0.33	0.28	-1.1e-7	2.8e-5	2.8e-5
[0°] layer	152	9.7	9.7	5.9	5.9	4.7	0.33	0.33	0.28	-1.1e-7	2.8e-5	2.8e-5
[90°] layer and Deltoid	9.7	152.0	9.7	5.9	4.7	5.9	0.021	0.28	0.33	2.8e-5	-1.0e-7	2.8e-5
Platform Braids	65.8	46.1	9.7	25.8	4.7	4.7	0.421	0.28	0.28	2.9e-6	1.2e-6	2.8e-5

Table 2

σ_{33c}	σ_{13c}	σ_{23c}	G_{Ic}	G_{IIc}	G_{IIIc}
45 MPa	35 MPa	35 MPa	300J/m ²	1000J/m ²	1000J/m ²